

Prospective Observational Evaluation of Pregnancy Induced Hypertension (PIH) and Intrauterine Growth Restriction (IUGR) in Primigravida using Doppler

Sweety Rani¹, Abha Rani Sinha², Renu Bharati³

¹Junior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, PMCH, Patna, Bihar, India

²Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, PMCH, Patna, Bihar, India

³Junior Resident, Department of Paediatrics, JLNMCH, Bhagalpur,

Received: 01-09-2023 / Received: 22-09-2023 / Accepted: 21-10-2023

Corresponding Author: Dr Renu Bharati

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to assess the role of doppler study in evaluation of pregnancy induced hypertension (PIH) and intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) in primigravida.

Methods: This Prospective observational study was carried out in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology at Patna Medical College and Hospital Patna, Bihar, India from January 2017 to December 2017. In our study a total of 100 Primigravida patients between 18 to 35 years of age, attending antenatal outpatient department, were screened at 18 to 22 weeks of gestation with USG along with Doppler study.

Results: All the patients' age ranged from 19 years to 35 years. 15% were in the age group of ≤ 20 years, Majority of the patients (49%) were in the age group of 21-25 years, 29% were in the age group between 26-30 years, least number of patients (7%) were seen in the age group of 31-35 years. The mean maternal age was 23.57 years. The study group included patients whose gestational age ranged from 18-22 weeks of gestation. Mean gestational age at the time of 1st scan was 22.18 weeks. The study group included patients whose gestational age ranged from 30-38 weeks of gestation. Mean gestational age at the time of 2nd scan was 32.48 weeks. 8 patients developed only PIH (3 PE + 5 GH); 9 patients had only IUGR and 7 patients were complicated by both PIH and IUGR.

Conclusion: Elevated uterine artery PI and presence of diastolic notch appears to be more significantly superior to other parameters in prediction of Preeclampsia. Umbilical artery Doppler findings are better predictor of perinatal outcome than abnormal MCA in early weeks of gestation whereas MCA PI Doppler is more useful than Umbilical PI or uterine artery in predicting the adverse perinatal outcome in later weeks.

Keywords: Uterine Artery Doppler, Pregnancy induced hypertension, Intrauterine growth restriction, Maternal Outcome, Neonatal Outcome

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Hypertensive disorders affect approximately 5-10% of all pregnancies worldwide. [1] It is the most typical medical condition in pregnancy. As a significant risk factor of maternal and perinatal mortality and morbidity globally, it accounts for almost 10-20% of pregnancy-related mortality in low and middle-income countries. [2] Hypertension during pregnancy results in uteroplacental insufficiency. It is considered a major contributing factor in adverse post-delivery outcomes such as newborn intensive care unit (NICU) admission, low birth weight, birth asphyxia, preterm birth, perinatal death, intrauterine growth restriction and stillbirth. [3]

As per the classification recommended by the National High Blood Pressure Education Program

Working Group on High Blood Pressure in Pregnancy, hypertensive disorders in pregnancy are classified as chronic hypertension, preeclampsia-eclampsia, pre-eclampsia superimposed on chronic hypertension, and gestational hypertension. [4] Doppler ultrasound, based on the physical principle first described by CA Doppler in 1842, states the change in frequency of a sound wave when a moving object reflects it provides a safe, non-invasive, and rapid method to assess uteroplacental and fetal circulation, which helps in examining the relationship of impaired blood flow to adverse perinatal outcome. [5,6]

The incidence of preeclampsia is 8%-10% in pregnant women, according to the National Health Portal of India. In India, the research found that the

frequency of hypertensive disorders during pregnancy was 7.8%, with preeclampsia (PE) occurring in 5.4% of the population. [7] Fetal growth restriction (FGR) and fetal distress that results due to fetal hypoxemia or asphyxia can be investigated using Doppler velocimetry of uteroplacental and fetoplacental circulations. [8] The placenta through implantation and development modifies the uterine circulation from one of low flow and high resistance to one of high flow and low resistance. The primary defect that predisposes pregnancy to uteroplacental complication appear to be partial/complete failure of trophoblastic invasion. [9] It is therefore desirable to know the accurate changes in uteroplacental and fetal circulation to predict perinatal outcome and help in appropriate intervention. It is here that role of Color Doppler comes. Doppler ultrasound examination is a non-invasive method, which gives useful information about impaired blood flow to the fetus at risk among high risk patients several studies suggested a significant decrease in neonatal morbidity & mortality when doppler evaluation was a part of fetal surveillance. [10] The rates of preterm birth, growth retarded foetuses and perinatal death, are significantly increased in pregnancies complicated by severe preeclampsia. [11,12]

The aim of the present study was to assess the role of doppler study in evaluation of pregnancy induced hypertension (PIH) and intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) in primigravida.

Materials and Methods

This Prospective observational study was carried out in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology at Patna Medical College and Hospital Patna, Bihar ,

India from January 2017 to December 2017 In our study a total of 100 Primigravida patients between 18 to 35 years of age, attending antenatal outpatient department, were screened at 18 to 22 weeks of gestation with USG along with Doppler study. Follow up Doppler studies were done after 30 weeks of gestation in the third trimester as per indicated to determine a favorable or worsening trend in Doppler indices. All the eligible candidates were included in the study depending on the following inclusion and exclusion criteria:

Inclusion Criteria: All Primigravida coming to our OPD. All Primigravida with singleton pregnancy.

Exclusion Criteria: Multiple gestations. Patients with history of medical disorders such as diabetes, hypertension, renal disease and cardiac disease. Unregistered Primigravida term gestation. All subjects with preterm labour and PROM. Congenital anomalies of uterus and fetus. Pregnant women of age less than 18 years and more than 35 years, or unknown last menstrual period. Intrauterine death at the time of first Doppler examination. Trophoblastic disease.

The data was coded and entered into Microsoft Excel spreadsheet. Analysis was done using Statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 20 (IBM SPSS Statistics Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA) Windows software program. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value and accuracy were also calculated for all Doppler measurements.

Results

Table 1: Age distribution

Age in years	N	%
≤20	15	15
21-25	49	49
26-30	29	29
31-35	7	7

All the patients' age ranged from 19 years to 35 years. 15% were in the age group of ≤20 years, Majority of the patients (49%) were in the age group of 21-25 years, 29% were in the age group between 26-30 years, least number of patients (7%) were seen in the age group of 31-35 years. The mean maternal age was 23.57 years.

Table 2: Distribution of patients according to gestational age at 1st scan (18-22 weeks) and at 2nd scan (After 30 weeks)

Gestational age at 1 st scan (weeks of gestation)	No. of Patients	Percentage (%)
18	22	22
19	14	14
20	23	23
21	17	17
22	24	24
Total	100	100
Mean	22.18	-
Std. Deviation	1.448	-
Gestational age at 2 nd scan (weeks of gestation)		

30	11	11
31	10	10
32	15	15
33	14	14
34	13	13
35	11	11
36	20	20
37	3	3
38	3	3
Total	100	100
Mean	32.48	-
Std. Deviation	2.220	-

The study group included patients whose gestational age ranged from 18-22 weeks of gestation. Mean gestational age at the time of 1st scan was 22.18 weeks. The study group included patients whose gestational age ranged from 30-38 weeks of gestation. Mean gestational age at the time of 2st scan was 32.48 weeks.

Table 3: Distribution of cases of pre-eclampsia (pe), gestational hypertension (gh) and intrauterine growth restriction (iugr) in study population

Outcome	No. of Patients	Percentage (%)	Total
(GH + IUGR)	8	8	-
PIH (PE + GH)	8	8	
IUGR	9	9	25
(PIH + IUGR)	7	7	
Normal Subjects	75	75	75
Total	-	-	100

8 patients developed only PIH (3 PE + 5 GH); 9 patients had only IUGR and 7 patients were complicated by both PIH and IUGR.

Table 4: Adverse pregnancy outcome in study population

OUTCOME	Number of patients					
	PIH (PE + GH)	IUGR	PIH + IUGR	Normal subjects	Total	
Gestational Age at delivery	<37 weeks	1	7	7	5	20
	37- 42weeks	7	1	0	72	80
	>42weeks	0	0	0	0	0
Birth Weight	<10th centile	0	8	7	0	15
	>10th centile	8	0	0	77	85
Stay in NICU	YES	1	9	7	4	23
	NO	7	0	0	72	77
APGAR at 1 minute	≤7	1	9	7	5	22
	>7	7	0	0	71	78
APGAR at 5 minute	≤7	1	9	7	3	20
	>7	7	0	0	73	80

Mean gestational age at time of delivery - 37.68 weeks. Preterm delivery – 20%. Term delivery – 80%. Minimum Birth weight - 1.42 kilograms. Maximum Birth weight -3.26 kilograms. Mean Birth weight at time of delivery - 2.7028 kilograms. Stay in NICU – 23%. Minimum stay in NICU – 3 days. Maximum stay in NICU – 14 days.

Discussion

Hypertensive disorder of pregnancy is one of the most common complication that effects human pregnancy. It is one of the leading cause of maternal & fetal mortality & morbidity. [13] It comprises 7-

10% of all pregnancies. Pregnancy Induced Hypertension includes Gestational hypertension, Pre-eclampsia and Eclampsia. PIH has many complications. The most common complication of PIH is Intra uterine growth retardation (IUGR). perinatal deaths - including intrauterine and early neonatal deaths, hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy intraventricular hemorrhage, periventricular leukomalacia, pulmonary hemorrhage and necrotizing enterocolitis. Minor outcomes included caesarean delivery for fetal distress, APGAR score below 7 at 5 minutes, admission to neonatal intensive care unit. Others are placental infarcts,

abruption. The main goals of prenatal testing are to identify fetuses at increased risk for perinatal morbidity & mortality. Early detection of disease would lead to an improved outcome, through increased surveillance and use of prophylactic therapies such as low dose aspirin. [14,15]

All the patients' age ranged from 19 years to 35 years. 15% were in the age group of ≤ 20 years, Majority of the patients (49%) were in the age group of 21-25 years, 29% were in the age group between 26-30 years, least number of patients (7%) were seen in the age group of 31-35 years. The mean maternal age was 23.57 years. The study group included patients whose gestational age ranged from 18-22 weeks of gestation. Mean gestational age at the time of 1st scan was 22.18 weeks. The study group included patients whose gestational age ranged from 30-38 weeks of gestation. Mean gestational age at the time of 2nd scan was 32.48 weeks. In Pregnancy induced hypertension there is inadequate invasion of spiral arteries leading to increased resistances in spiral arteries. This leads to increased impedance of blood flow in uterine arteries Fleischer A, Schulman H, Farmakides G et al 1986. [16] The findings in our study are consistent with above. In our study of uterine artery Doppler velocimetry among 41 case group, 15 (36.53%) subjects had normal flow pattern in uterine artery and 26 (63.46%) had abnormal flow pattern with raised indices and diastolic notches. Out of 26 cases of PIH showing raised Doppler indices and diastolic notch, 14 cases showed bilateral abnormality (B), either raised indices, diastolic notch or both leading to (34.1%) cases of total. Our findings were consistent with Mohd Khalid et al (2011) [17] to determine the role of Color Doppler Sonography in evaluation of fetal outcome in 58 antenatal females (22 normotensive, 36 hypertensive) in their third trimester of pregnancy. Arteries evaluated included – bilateral uterine arteries, umbilical artery, fetal middle cerebral and fetal aorta. In this study, 34(94.44%) out of 36 hypertensive patients showed abnormal uterine artery flow. U/L Uterine artery involved in 12 cases (33.3%). B/L uterine artery was involved in 22 (61.11%) cases. Axt-Flidner Ret al (2004) [18] in a Prospective study to assess the role of uterine artery color Doppler waveform analysis in the prediction of adverse pregnancy outcome such as preeclampsia, intrauterine growth retardation, placental abruption or a combination of outcome parameters in risk pregnancies (n=52). According Jackson MR et al [19], patients with uterine artery notches and high resistance flow had significantly higher rates of fetal growth retardation and caesarean delivery because of fetal distress and had significantly bad pregnancy outcome.

8 patients developed only PIH (3 PE + 5 GH); 9 patients had only IUGR and 7 patients were complicated by both PIH and IUGR. Mean

gestational age at time of delivery - 37.68 weeks. Preterm delivery – 20%. Term delivery – 80%. Minimum Birth weight - 1.42 kilograms. Maximum Birth weight -3.26 kilograms. Mean Birth weight at time of delivery - 2.7028 kilograms. Stay in NICU – 23%. Minimum stay in NICU – 3 days. Maximum stay in NICU – 14 days. The umbilical artery represents the fetoplacental system which primarily reflects placental resistance and is the primary vessel for monitoring high-risk pregnancies. Various studies reported abnormal umbilical artery PI and S/D ratio as factors influencing adverse pregnancy outcomes like intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), neonatal death and low Apgar score. [20,21] Park et al. also suggested the consequence of notch depth in the presence of diastolic notch to predict poor perinatal outcomes. [22] Also, it is observed that adverse outcomes were substantially higher amongst cases with abnormal fetal MCA measurements and abnormal CPR (p-value <0.05). Similar findings were observed in other studies. [23,24]

According to Ochi, et al [25] increased PI and the presence of diastolic notch in the uterine artery flow velocity, indicate increased uterine arterial resistance and impaired uterine circulation. The findings in the present study suggest that the increased Doppler indices in uterine artery with associated diastolic notch and persistence of diastolic notch after 30 weeks of gestation constitute an ominous sign and indicate the requirement for timely and intense fetal surveillance and intervention. The present study concludes that elevated uterine artery PI and presence of diastolic notch at early weeks of gestation appears to be a better predictor and more significant than uterine artery S/D in assessment of intrauterine fetal growth and in predicting perinatal outcome.

Conclusion

Elevated uterine artery PI and presence of diastolic notch appears to be more significantly superior to other parameters in prediction of Preeclampsia. Umbilical artery Doppler findings are better predictor of perinatal outcome than abnormal MCA in early weeks of gestation whereas MCA PI Doppler is more useful than Umbilical PI or uterine artery in predicting the adverse perinatal outcome in later weeks.

References

1. Hutcheon JA, Lisonkova S, Joseph KS. Epidemiology of pre-eclampsia and the other hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. *Best Pract Res Clin Obstet Gynaecol.* 2011 Aug; 25 (4):391-403.
2. Magee LA, von Dadelszen P, Stones W, Mathai M. The FIGO textbook of pregnancy hypertension: an evidence-based guide to

- monitoring, prevention and management. The Global Library of Women's Medicine; 2016.
3. Berhe AK, Ilesanmi AO, Aimakhu CO, Mulugeta A. Effect of pregnancy induced hypertension on adverse perinatal outcomes in Tigray regional state, Ethiopia: a prospective cohort study. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*. 2019 Dec 31;20(1):7.
 4. Program NH. Report of the national high blood pressure education program working group on high blood pressure in pregnancy. *American journal of obstetrics and gynecology*. 2000 Jul 1;183(1):s1-22.
 5. Katsi V, Felekos I, Kallikazaros I. Christian Andreas Doppler: A legendary man inspired by the dazzling light of the stars. *Hippokratia*. 2013 Apr;17(2):113-4.
 6. Aharwal S, Agrawal R, Sharma S. A study of role of Doppler ultrasound in pregnancy-induced hypertension (PIH) and perinatal outcome. *Int J Med Res Rev*. 2016;4(4):672-.
 7. Sajith M, Nimbargi V, Modi A, Sumariya R, Pawar A. Incidence of pregnancy induced hypertension and prescription pattern of antihypertensive drugs in pregnancy. *Int J Pharma Sci Res*. 2014;23:4.
 8. Vergani P, Roncaglia N, Andreotti C, Arreghini A, Teruzzi M, Pezzullo JC, Ghidini A. Prognostic value of uterine artery Doppler velocimetry in growth-restricted fetuses delivered near term. *Am J Obstet Gynecol*. 2002 Oct;187(4):932-6.
 9. Khong, T. DeWolf, F. Robertson, Inadequate maternal vascular response to placentation in pregnancies complicated by Pre eclampsia.
 10. Newnham JP, O'Dea MRA, Reid KP, et al. Doppler flow velocity waveform analysis in high risk pregnancies : a randomized controlled trial. *Br. J. ObstetGynecol* 1991; 98 : 956-963.
 11. Lin CC, Lindheimer MD, River P. Fetal outcome in hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. *Am J ObstetGynecol* 1982; 142:255.
 12. Sibai B, Spinnato JA, Watson DL. Pregnancy outcome in 303 cases with severe preeclampsia. *ObstetGynecol* 1984; 64:319-321.
 13. Zeeman GG, Dekkor GA: Pathogenesis of preeclampsia: a hypothesis. *Clin Obstet Gynecol* 1992; 35 : 317-337.
 14. Mc Parland, P. Peare, J. M., Chamberlain, G. V., Doppler sonography and aspirin in prevention of pregnancy induced hypertension. [PubMed]
 15. Uza, Hadda, (1994) Uteroplacental Doppler, *Ultrasound Obs and Gynaecol*, 4.
 16. Fleischer A, Schulman H, Farmakides G, et al. Uterine artery doppler primary in pregnant women with hypertension. *Am J ObstetGynecol* 1986; 154 : 806-813. [PubMed]
 17. Mohd Khalid1, Shagufta Wahab1, Vijay Kumar1, Saifullah Khalid1, Soafia Haroon2, Noor A. Sabzposh2 Doppler Indices in Prediction of Fetal Outcome in Hypertensive Pregnant Women *NJOG* 2011 May-June; 6 (1): 28-34.
 18. Axt-Flidner R, Schwarze A, Nelles I, Altgassen C, Friedrich M, Schmidt W, Diedrich K The value of uterine artery Doppler ultrasound in the prediction of severe complications in a risk population.
 19. Jakson M.R., Walsh A.J., Marrow, R.J., Mullen J.B. et al.: Reduced placental villous free elaboration in small for gestational age pregnancies, relationship with umbilical artery Doppler waveform. *Am. J. ObstetGynecol*, 1995; 8, 172, (2 pt.I) 518-25.
 20. Ayyuba R, Abubakar IS, Yakasai IA. Umbilical artery Doppler velocimetry study on prediction of adverse pregnancy outcomes among pregnant women with hypertensive disorders in Kano, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Basic and Clinical Sciences*. 2015 Jul 1;12(2): 95-104.
 21. Sharma P, Gyawali M, Gurung SD. Role of umbilical artery Doppler in predicting intrauterine growth restriction and foetal outcome in pregnant ladies with pregnancy induced hypertension. *Nepalese Journal of Radiology*. 2017;7(1-2):3-8.
 22. Park YW, Cho JS, Choi HM, Kim TY, Lee SH, Yu JK, Kim JW. Clinical significance of early diastolic notch depth: uterine artery Doppler velocimetry in the third trimester. *Am J Obstet Gynecol*. 2000 May;182(5):1204-9.
 23. Khalid M, Wahab S, Kumar V, Khalid S, Haroon S, Sabzposh NA. Doppler indices in prediction of fetal outcome in hypertensive pregnant women. *Nepal Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology*. 2011;6(1):28-34.
 24. Eser A, Zulfikaroglu E, Eserdag S, Kılıc S, Danisman N. Predictive value of middle cerebral artery to uterine artery pulsatility index ratio in preeclampsia. *Arch Gynecol Obstet*. 2011 Aug;284(2):307-11.
 25. Ochi H, Matsubara K, Kusanagi Y, Taniguchi H, Ito M. Significance of a diastolic notch in the uterine artery flow velocity waveform induced by uterine embolisation in the pregnant ewe. *Br J Obstet Gynaecol*. 1998; 105 (10):1118- 21.